

Choosing Measures for Energy Efficient Hospital Buildings

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Abstract — The improvement of the energy efficiency of a complex system such as an existing large non-residential building, requires multi-disciplinary engineering knowledge, practices and teams, as well as support from equally complex software tools and modelling methodologies, especially during the initial planning and feasibility assessment phases of relevant projects. In this paper, the peculiarities of the special case of hospital buildings are discussed and a number of use cases are described, identifying significant components and setting the basic needed tooling interventions and methodology steps in order to address the complexity of assessment of different energy conservation measures.

Keywords—*Energy efficient hospitals; building energy consumption modelling tools; building automation systems; energy conservation measures*

I. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

The importance of the building sector's energy consumption is already widely acknowledged, as this is proven by the relevant activity intensities at the state policy creation level [1] or at the financial and commercial arena [2]. Besides the global quests for efficient and sustainable usage of the planet resources and for the reduction of carbon emissions, this special focus on the building sector is highly attributed to the fact that the sector is mainly responsible for the 40% of the total energy consumption in the developed part of the world, as well as to the identified initial margin of possible improvements and resulting mid and long term financial gains, especially at large commercial and other public buildings.

This latter fact is the main motivating force behind the well-established main business model of the Energy Saving (or Servicing) Companies (ESCOs), being, in short, either the providers of the technical know-how for energy consumption or CO₂ reductions, or the providers of the typically high initial capital investment needed for an energy consumption and efficiency improvement intervention in a foreign building, and then the owners of a share of the annual financial gains that arise from this intervention and for a specific contract duration. This activity, in turn, calls for a careful and as accurate as possible assessment, in both technical and financial dimensions, of any possible retrofit or other set of Energy Conservation Measures (ECM) for the existing building at hand, before the terms and duration of the relevant contract between the ESCO and the building owner are set. Furthermore, as the building population becomes newer or already retrofitted once, and as the policy targets are set towards a Zero Energy Building (ZEB), or when there is a predefined acceptable ROI timeframe, it becomes harder and harder to apply the typical recipes with known large initial impact, and a more detailed analysis is needed to address the squeezed efficiency and profit gain margins. The significance of the latter must be not underestimated, as it was possibly the case even for policy creators in the early stages, a discrepancy though that is already identified and started to be addressed [3].

Quantification and prediction of a building's energy consumption is a complex task, considering the large parameter space and the typically non-linear dynamics of large and important basic elements of the process. The problem becomes heavier if we considered the fact that predictions at hand may refer to a forward time in terms of years, as well as for a building that may be completely different than the currently assessed, since the application of any set of radical ECMs may completely change its behavior – as this is the objective many times, if it is to become more energy efficient. Thus, models of this building operation's aspect are the main and only tools to assess and decide on the financial feasibility of any candidate set of technically applicable ECMs.

The engineering and scientific literature is a rich source of proposed or widely accepted relevant models and modelling techniques, referring to partial or whole building energy consumption characterization. Selected recent and indicative reviews and classifications can be found in [4]-[9], but in some simple and rough dimensioning, although using slightly different terminology for the same underlying principles, the various approaches can be classified as physical / statistical / hybrid or white / black / grey, which is close to calculation-based / measurement-based / hybrid, and close to engineering / statistical / hybrid classifications, all

aligned to the classical (forward) and data-driven (inverse) relevant classification of [10], with their dynamic or steady-state variances.

Qualitative comparison frameworks can be also found in [7]-[8], based on complex or simple dimensions, such as on the axis of application and use-case, on the level of building details or on the amount of measurement data needed, on the computation time and on the level of insight to the underlying physical processes revealed. Quantitative comparisons do exist in the currently available literature, too. The early study in [11] compares the traditional (multiple) regression analysis with a decision tree and a neural network based methods, and while it shows that both other approaches can be viable alternatives to the regression models, the authors' findings include the fact that different models perform better on summer or winter data, and different overlapping sets of influencing factors are identified as significant. Furthermore, in [12], a simple artificial neural network (ANN) based model and a forward, physical simulation model (EnergyPlus) are compared as predicting tools for energy consumption forecasting for a non-residential building. Results demonstrate that both models are suitable for prediction, and the parametric analysis carried out on EnergyPlus reveals as most important influencing factors the internal heat gains and the equipment performance. However, the simple ANN model is not suggested as a tool for the evaluation of different potential energy reduction strategies. Finally, it is shown that the occupants' behavior may significantly affect the accuracy of predictions (under-predicting in hotter days and over-predicting in colder days). On the other hand, authors in [13] focus on Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) system level models, comparing gray-box with black-box models based on multiple-input and multiple-output (MIMO) ANN, transfer function (TF), process, state-space (SS) and autoregressive exogenous (ARX) methods for various HVAC subsystems. They show that the ANN outperforms the other modelling methods followed by the ARX, TF, SS, and gray-box models. Finally, studies such as in [8] suggest that no all approaches fit all purposes, with the forward and calibrated models being ranked as better for the purposes of retrofit and ECM alternatives assessment.

Whatever the chosen approach is, the literature also reveals results that may even come from large datasets regarding the base parameters that affect various energy end-uses, their significance on the degree they affect the final energy consumption, the weights of each end-use, as well as the dependencies among them, such as the relationship of the space heating/cooling energy and the gains from electrical loads, being also energy consumers themselves. In this respect, top energy end-uses for general commercial buildings are considered the space conditioning, lighting and water heating, followed by ventilation, refrigeration, computers and miscellaneous electrical loads, while most important parameters include the climate and weather conditions, the occupants behavior, the building characteristics and the building systems structure, characteristics and conditions. However, studies or results referring to the wide space of "non-residential" buildings may become inaccurate or at least untrusted when the focus closes on a strict subset with very distinct characteristics, such as the hospital buildings.

The structure of the paper is as follows: in the next section, the special characteristics of the hospital building case are discussed. Then, section III presents the overall modelling methodology followed in this work, while section IV presents the case studies and the results on two different hospital building cases. The developed tool interventions are described in section IV while section V concludes the paper.

II. THE CASE OF HOSPITAL BUILDINGS

Hospital buildings are characterized by a number of important differences among the large set of non-residential / commercial buildings. The first one refers to the continuous operation in contrast to most other building types in the subset which, more or less, follow the typical weekly working hour pattern. More accurately, they differ in the mix of embodied space types, having a higher percentage of space types that require a continuous usage. In fact, these percentages and their exact mix define also important sub-classes of hospital buildings, mainly referring to the degree of in-patient or out-patient orientation of their purpose and operation.

The second difference arises again from the high percentage of included space types with special indoor environment requirements. Such requirements can be easily found in the various countries' building codes, however it is easily understood that patient rooms with sensitive and ill people or infection free intensive care units and typically low temperature and light intensive operating rooms pose strict requirements on thermal and other indoor air quality attributes.

Finally, hospitals include a highly heterogeneous set of energy hungry large electrical equipment, such as MRI and other similar medical machines, which affect the final total building energy consumption mainly according to their usage schedules and patterns. The latter, in turn, is the most indicative and self-explanatory paradigm of showing the importance of the difference between the data describing the "as-designed" or "as-built" and the "as used" cases of a building. It is usually the most problematic part of the data collection in order to understand and model the energy consumption of the building, if no special sub-metering equipment is installed or if no process auditing plans are being used. In fact, the operation schedules and the actual activity patterns refer mainly to the occupancy related loads of many space types, such as ventilation, heating or cooling needs, lighting and other electrical loads from miscellaneous equipment, that should be known if the benefits from widely known or other innovative

building automation measures are to be calculated beforehand, as for example is the case with demand controlled ventilation (DCV), as well as space lighting and conditioning based on occupancy sensors.

With the advent and spread of sub-metering and other sensor based monitoring infrastructures the knowledge on this matter, on a per building basis, is expected to be substantially enhanced. However, so far there is only information coming from indicative audits or measurement campaigns and national data regressions [14]-[20], showing sometimes contradictory results, due to the differences in each hospital's kind, nature and location.

III. MODELLING APPROACH

Following the results of [8], the focus comes on the "forward" and "calibrated" models, indicated as a better starting point for the purpose of ECM assessments. Under this calculation-based class of methods the two main sub-categories include dynamic and steady-state methods. Dynamic methods refer to detailed, sub-hourly level dynamic simulations, where all details of physical parameters of the building envelope and HVAC, lighting and other subsystems are included, coupled with activity, operation schedules and weather information in order to calculate the final source energy uses and total consumption. A typical and well known dynamic simulator, widely used in the engineering and research community, is the open source EnergyPlus simulator [21], coupled with modelling GUIs and parametric analysis front-ends, such as the also open-source OpenStudio [22], all coming and supported from the NREL Lab of the US Energy Department. The objective of the steady-state methods, on the other hand, is to simplify the dynamic simulations, by reducing the needed inputs and the processing time. Typical steady-state forward models are the ones adopted from current European EPBD related and international standard provisions [23]-[25], incorporating all complex dynamic effects through offline calculated – typically at a country and regional level - correlation factors, called utilization factors. Monthly and hourly methods are supported, depending mainly on the formal provisions of each country for their national labeling calculations for non-residential buildings.

Still, as it is extracted from the literature review and the common engineering practices, the target objective is the definition of easily used static functional models, that can be then applied to the various phases of typical energy efficiency project flows, either as a whole or as part, as for example in adjusting baseline consumptions to current / future conditions in the design and execution of a Measurement & Validation (M&V) plan [26], or in assessments of alternative ECM measures and optimal structures or settings in a holistic context, including financial aspects [27]. However, in seeking such target static models, it is not clear whether all important measurement data from real functional buildings as needed will be available, and the most often case is that they are not – at least until upcoming regulations for sub-metering infrastructures take place. Thus, in order for the data analysis methods to be safely applicable in the course of the modelling phases, useful data sets can be also produced through simulations in a manageable and flexible environment of different parameter and condition settings. Simulations can be based either on first order complex models as they are exploited by dynamic simulators like EnergyPlus, or on simplified steady state or dynamic models and methods proposed by relative Energy Performance Building Directive standards.

This paper focuses on the dynamic simulation approach, using the open-source OpenStudio / EnergyPlus as the base modelling framework. For this, it uses two distinct cases of hospital buildings. The first one refers to the virtual hospital created by the NREL and used in the Advanced Energy Design Guide (AEDG) for Large Hospitals [28]. The purpose of the work in [28] was to demonstrate the large initial margin of possible improvements by adopting heavy changes mainly in the structure and technologies used for the HVAC components and systems. The purpose of our work on this virtual hospital was to also focus on a certain system structure and identify the significance of the main parameters of its operation in the final energy consumption of the whole building. The second case is a real hospital from south Italy, which was modeled based on recent data available from a previous energy audit that was kindly provided to us. In all cases, after a running model has been created for a dynamic simulator, it can be used as a generator engine of high accuracy data that can be used in multiple ways, with the main free elementary parameter holding blocks being:

- The location of the building and its climate, being a virtual Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) weather file or an Actual Meteorological Year (AMY) weather file
- The structure and the materials of its walls and windows
- The structure and sizing of its HVAC (air) system and components and their operational settings
- The structure and sizing of its plant (water) system and components and their operational settings
- The load requirements for each space, i.e. the maximum number of expected occupants (for equipment sizing), the schedule of occupancy and the explicit maximum and scheduled numbers for electrical and miscellaneous heating & cooling loads

Interventions in energy source provisioning such as renewable energy or co-generation installations have been left out from the current analysis step, while important remarks that should be mentioned, arising from the inherent capabilities of the EnergyPlus simulator, include the lack of any automatic connection between occupancy schedules and correlated results on other parameters such as electrical loads, infiltration changes due to the activities variation at each occupancy scheduling step. That is, changing of occupancy figures will result to a change of the heating/cooling loads due to respective internal gains for the relevant space, but not any other, typically correlated load such as the additional electrical and heating/cooling loads from the equipment used by the occupants, or infiltration changes resulting by the occupants acting on doors and windows.

Besides this, it must be also made clear that certain changes before a simulation run for the same weather file might completely change the building structure, which is not always what is expected, for all uses of the simulator. For example, a change in the maximum occupancy (design day) values or a change in an envelope material in the original model file, will create a totally different HVAC and plant system, since the simulator executes an automatic equipment sizing step before the actual yearly simulation. Thus, for each selected original model, there is a porting effort to the typical climate and envelope structure of a new (virtual) location or weather file, and then this new model file is also split to 2 versions: one with the auto-sizing feature enabled, in order to study the effects of radical changes in design requirements, running conditions and HVAC/plant configurations, and one statically sized, resulting in a fixed building which can be then virtually "audited", providing also a platform to test the results of operational parameter changes without changing the capacity of the equipment.

IV. SELECTED USE CASES

Acting on this latter case of the statically sized AEDG virtual hospital ported to the Milan TMY climatic conditions, and after the proper instrumentation of the model with a large number of probes and virtual metering devices, a rich set of data have been collected on an hourly basis. From this set, and after plotting the recorded data in different time or scatter configurations, basic relationships between the various components of gas and electricity consumption have been extracted, as for example the dominance of the heating gas consumption in the overall facility consumption, in contrast to the facility-wide electricity consumption, where the dominance stems from the other, mainly scheduled, components. This is also visible in the attempts to model consumptions as dependencies of the outdoor temperature only, where there can be descend estimates in all cases, except for the total facility electrical consumption (judging on the basis of the co-efficient of determination, R^2).

Following the more typical use of the simulator capabilities, it is possible to identify the parameters and control knobs that are mostly influential to the consumption components and can be targets of certain optimizations. After an extensive simulation campaign studying mainly the effects of envelope elements, occupancy schedules and equipment set-points [29], for this particular system structure it was evident that among the most significant parameters were the flow and temperature set-points, and especially the HVAC central supply air temperature - taking into account that the air flow set-points, although highly influential, are typically bounded by regulations and relative building codes.

Fig. 1. Seasonal Electricity & Gas use vs. Supply Air Temperature (SAT) for the AEDG VAV-based Virtual Hospital

The results of multiple simulations over TMY weather data with increasing supply air temperature settings are depicted in Fig. 1. Using these data, it is possible to extract faster estimators that may demonstrate $R^2 \sim 0.93$ and RMSE equal to 316MJ & 41kWh for heating and cooling energy consumption, respectively, when applied to AMY weather data (2015).

However, apart from the feasibility of the approach, the above results reveal also the fact that the choice of the baseline version of the AEDG virtual hospital structure is somehow artificially too much energy inefficient, as there is a substantial overlap of heating and cooling consumption throughout the year. This can be attributed to the chosen distribution of zones with substantially differing ventilation requirements in each VAV loop, while in high percentages of required fresh outdoor air and in the absence of a heat exchanger, as well as by the fact that the plant structure is modelled by virtual aggregate single large boiler and chiller loops. Thus, a second case is based on the detailed model of an existing real hospital, following the complex structure of all real installations of air systems and water plant equipment.

The hospital is a mid-size 4+1 floor building with a total size of ~6000 m², located to a relatively hot and humid part of South Italy, as presented in Fig. 2. Its HVAC systems consist of a set of 16 rooftop heat-pumps providing hot and chilled water to the 19 Air Handling Units (AHUs) and their relative air loops of the required conditioned outdoor air, as well as to a set of final space conditioning Fan Coil Units (FCUs), while a small number of spaces are conditioned by newer Variable Refrigerant Flow (VRF) systems. As an indicative example, the structure of the AHU12 air loop, along with the 3 related and FCU conditioned hospital zones, appears in Fig. 3. In this example the cooling, heating and post-heating coils of the central outdoor air system are modelled separately, tightened to the appropriate chill/hot and heat recovery water loops of the relevant heat pump structure (heat pumps 1, 2 and 5 in this case).

Fig. 2. OpenStudio / EnergyPlus Real Hospital Model (South Italy)

Fig. 3. AHU12 Air Loop structure supporting 3 hospital zones with FCUs (South Italy)

Fig. 4. Modeled and actual monthly energy consumption (South Italy)

While calibrated models based on the monthly energy bills are certainly possible to be achieved, as it appears in Fig. 4, they should be still used with caution, since there are important crucial intermediate or input parameters that have never been measured or audited, leaving thus quite large space of freedom to the modeler during the calibration process. In any case, there is a substantial difference in behavior and in applicability of smaller, nonintrusive candidate measures between the model of a real structure and the model of an aggregate virtual one when it comes to the comparison of changes in the properties of real equipment and zone level parameters and schedules. As it happens with the structure of requested input data from other tools based on the EPBD simplified monthly or hourly methods (e.g. SBEM), the whole building behavior is better approximated as a sum of different zone or loop behaviors with varying characteristics. Thus, reverse modelling approaches like system identification are expected to provide more flexibility if they are structured as a sum of sub-system inverse models, and the same applies for the minimum required sub-metering plans, when available. Furthermore, as each building, even of the same class e.g. a hospital building, has its own characteristic function which can be hardly generalized as a whole, then by focusing the quest of simplified, fast, reverse models in basic elementary constructs, it will be possible to derive a general approach which will be capable to be applied in a large population of buildings by changing only the contribution weights of each elementary model. In this way, for example, it will be feasible to have a common basic model describing equally well an in-patient or an out-patient medical facility by presenting a variance in the contribution weights of e.g. the energy sub-model of a patient room aggregate zone supported by a Dedicated Outdoor Air System (DOAS) and FCUs sub-system structure, but still offering this particular element's black-box significant parameters for tuning instead of hiding the whole elementary structure under a simpler and very generic variable, e.g. a simple scalar efficiency figure for the whole HVAC system & plant. In conclusion, the target static functional model has the form of (1), where F_i the consumption model describing sub-system i , and X_i the input variables vector of F_i .

$$\sum_{i=0}^n F_i(\overline{X_i}) \quad (1)$$

V. TOOL INTERVENTIONS

In order to orchestrate and automate the creation of the needed datasets for sensitivity analysis and inverse model creation, the Parametric Analysis Tool (PAT) of the OpenStudio suite was exploited. In this process, a number of Ruby scripts from the Building Component Library (BCL) were modified in order to be applicable to the version of our hospital models, such as the ones which radically change the structure and the technologies of the HVAC systems (e.g. change everything with VRF). However, since the focus was also in identifying relationships with controllable parameters of stable structures, such as their operational set-points and their usage schedules, a set of ruby scripts were created and added to the parametric analysis chain.

These tool extensions include Ruby measure scripts for controlling the output of variable probes, for changing the plant availability schedules and plans, based either on temporal or weather parameters, on changing the zone set-points, the central outdoor air temperature set-points, the final zone equipment heating and cooling air temperature set-points, as well as the water plant temperatures and resets. An example of the interface of the created measure scripts, as it appears from inside the OpenStudio GUI is presented in Fig. 5, referring to a temperature-based plant availability plan setting measure.

Name
Setup VST HVAC Plant Availability
Description
Setup VST HVAC Plant Availability. Temperature-based On/Off
Modeler Description
Setup VST HVAC Plant Availability. Temperature-based On/Off
Inputs
Heating On Temperature The OA temperature below which the heating is turned on.
10.5
Heating Off Temperature The OA temperature above which the heating is turned off.
20.3
Cooling On Temperature The OA temperature above which the cooling is turned on.
25
Cooling Off Temperature The OA temperature below which the cooling is turned off.
17

Fig. 5. Interface of a plant availability plan setting measure

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In seeking improvements of the energy efficiency of a hospital building, the structure of HVAC systems, their set-points and the various operation schedules are the most influential parameter sets, besides the main weather influence. In support of educated decisions, no other modelling practice can capture such differences except forward calculations and dynamic simulations. But still, no forward simulation can be safely calibrated without actual data for important intermediate sub-system variables or even simulation inputs such lighting, activity and occupancy related schedules, along with their correlations among them. Sub-metering is the forthcoming solution to alleviate this, while data analysis from other hospitals may create appropriate distributions of combined inputs for these schedules. Finally, a set of tool interventions in the form of ruby scripts were introduced, which were used to orchestrate and automate the parametric analysis applied to a real hospital building model, producing also the needed output datasets for building and sub-system level inverse model creation using system identification techniques.

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